

Decoding Smells in *Das Parfum*

Seoyeong Ahn, Nour Alassali, Nina Olenderek, and Marieke van Erp

Introduction

This study decodes the relationship between olfactory experiences and social classes in *Das Parfum*. Using the Odeuropa project's smell extractor tool, we created a dataset of scent-related terms from the novel. Our analyses include a quantitative and qualitative overview of the olfactory landscape.

Research Question

How does *Das Parfum* depict the complex dynamics of social classes and olfactory experiences in the historical setting of 18th-century France?

1 Preprocessing

We used the Odeuropa extraction tool to gather scent-related words. Further preprocessing in R and Python—handling missing values, tokenizing words, removing stop words, and punctuation—was needed to align the data with our research goals.

2 Word Clouds

Smell word clouds illustrating the frequency and significance of olfactory terms linked with different socioeconomic classes (Poor and Rich) in *Das Parfum*.

odoriferous
effluvium
smoking odor
smell
inhaled
stank
whiff
scent
aroma
stinking smells

Poor

smells scents scented
cologne perfume perfumes
essence
fragrant smelled odor
effluvium
inhaled odors smell
rolled aromatic

Rich

How did we distinguish different socioeconomic classes (Rich & Poor)?

We have manually selected excerpts from the novel that describe various locations, such as a bustling fish market portraying the poor class, and an elegant perfume shop epitomizing the rich class.

3 Venn Diagram

Venn Diagram Showing the Intersection of Smell Sources Description between the Rich, Poor, and General Human Smell

4 Frequency Table

Top 5 Smell Sources and their Frequencies in Poor, Rich, and Human in General Categories

Discussion

Clear link between olfactory description and social classes

The poor often had unpleasant body odours, and the rich, fearing the odours emanating from the lower classes (Corbin, 2016, p. 232), could mask theirs with perfumes and other fragrances (Corbin, 2016, p. 276).

The rich social class's olfactory sources included floral words such as "tuberose," "jasmine," "rose," "jonquil flowers," and "lily." Indeed, among the bourgeoisie, it was fashionable to decorate homes and greenhouses with flowers like tuberose, jasmine, golden stock flowers, and forget-me-nots (Corbin, 2016, p. 300).

Being one of the highest frequency smell sources in poor social class, "kitchen" included smells from exposed trash cans beneath the kitchen sink, the musty odour of detergent, and the smell of the vent (Corbin, 2016, p. 259).

Link to GitHub

